

Deterministic Structures in Bi-gravitational Fields: A Unified Model Bridging Black Hole Singularities and Quantum Topology

Alfonso De Miguel Bueno*

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Abstract

This paper proposes a deterministic model that aims to unify the gravitational, strong, weak, and electromagnetic interactions by examining the intersections of gravitational fields. The model draws upon bigravity theories, where interactions between two metric tensors associated with coupled curvatures drive changes in spacetime curvature. By coupling expanding and contracting gravitational fields, the model reinterprets singularities — typically viewed as infinite points in spacetime curvature — as abrupt, yet finite changes in curvature direction and, in some cases, its sign. This perspective bridges the behavior

*Independent researcher — ademiguelbueno@gmail.com
Madrid, Spain.

of singularities across both quantum and cosmological scales. The shared nucleus formed by these intersecting fields provides new insights into energy transfer, density distribution, and information preservation. Furthermore, the model addresses key theoretical challenges, including the nature of dark matter, reflection positivity, the mass gap problem, and the physical significance of Hodge cycles, offering a fresh approach to understanding the limitations of General Relativity in describing atomic and black hole structures. An additional Appendix on a purely relativistic interpretation of gravitational acceleration in the context of a single gravitational field is provided at the end of the article.

1 Introduction

In 2020, Roger Penrose was awarded the Nobel Prize in Physics for his work demonstrating the existence of black hole singularities—points of extreme curvature where density and gravity become infinite—within the framework of Einstein’s General Relativity.

Although it remains a theoretical model, Penrose mathematically demonstrated that the gravitational collapse of massive stars leads to a process of extreme compression, culminating in the formation of a curvature singularity where density and the gravitational field reach infinity, resulting in the creation of a black hole. Other researchers, such as Kip Thorne, have modeled black hole formation by studying binary black hole mergers and the resulting gravitational waves.

Mathematically, singularities are characterized as

points where a curve abruptly changes direction or sign, forming a sharp cusp where a tangent cannot be defined. Such a singular point is described as a point-like region of undefined or infinite curvature.

Within the framework of General Relativity, which models gravity as a consequence of spacetime curvature, such a curvature singularity represents a point where gravitational forces become infinitely strong. This leads to a breakdown of the laws of General Relativity, highlighting the need for a more comprehensive theory to fully describe the behavior of spacetime in the presence of curvature singularities, which are considered extreme conditions.

The static universe model, prevalent at the beginning of the 20th century, was a foundational assumption in Einstein’s original General Relativity theory. To maintain a static gravitational field, Einstein introduced a cosmological constant — an outward-pushing force — to compensate for the inward gravitational pull caused by spacetime curvature.

However, in 1922, Alexander Friedmann developed solutions to Einstein’s General Relativity equations that demonstrated that the universe, as a curved spacetime manifold, could be dynamically changing — either expanding or contracting — instead of being static. Friedmann’s solutions showed that, depending on the universe’s density and the cosmological constant, different evolutionary scenarios involving contraction and expansion were possible, laying the groundwork for modern cyclic cosmology.

2 Singularities as Abrupt Changes in Curvature

In this paper, we propose a novel model in which black holes emerge from the intersection of two merging gravitational fields whose curvature periodically varies in or out of phase. This intersection forms a nucleus composed of two vertical and two transverse gravitational subfields, which are characterized as black holes with an inner singularity point where gravitational forces remain finite.

Additionally, the model posits that similar singularities exist in the curvature of subatomic field parti-

cles, being integrated into the nucleus proposed by a deterministic dual atomic model formed by two intersecting gravitational fields varying in or out of phase.

Under this framework, black holes and subatomic particles share identical topological structures, wherein curvature singularities involve abrupt changes in sign or direction. These singularities contrast with the gradually changing, smooth curvature predicted by General Relativity, possibly resulting in the failure of Einstein’s equations.

Figure 1: *Singularities in the symmetric system when both intersecting fields contract.*

Conceptually, our model shares a link with Gerard ’t Hooft’s work, particularly in exploring connections between black holes and subatomic particles through a deterministic framework, although it differs in both approach and results.

The intersecting gravitational fields produce two vertical and two transverse subfields. The vertical subfields resemble inverted cones of light meeting at their apex, while the transverse subfields resemble mirrored regions connected at a cusp singularity. This apex marks the intersection of the gravitational fields, creating regions of positive, negative, or mixed curvature.

In string theory, curvature singularities emerge as Calabi-Yau conifold cusps, with various mechanisms proposed to resolve the resulting infinities by introducing extended fundamental objects and extra dimensions to smooth spacetime curvature, aiming to unify quantum mechanics and General Relativity.

We relate the transverse subfields and their singularities to topological features such as conifold sin-

gularities and Calabi-Yau transverse regions, akin to those in string theory, though our approach to compactifying additional dimensions is distinct. This framework maintains finite gravitational forces at singularity points, offering a unified view of spacetime geometry.

Our model conceptualizes the transverse subfields, their singularities, and elliptic orbits as curved, "trapped" folds within a dual system, providing a relativistic interpretation of their hyperdimensionality. Additional spatial coordinates are necessary to describe the transverse subfields because their Y-axis would be considered from the perspective of their host gravitational fields as a diagonal, introducing dilation or contraction in the resultant measures of space and time. Additionally, a second time dimension is needed to describe the differences in phase between the nuclear subfields and their respective hosts, or the different phases between the mirror subfields when antisymmetry is introduced.

On the other hand, the intersecting fields model may be thought of as related to bigravity theories.

3 Bigravity Theory and Its Relation to the Intersecting Fields Model

Bigravity theory primarily emerged as a cosmological theory that modifies general relativity by introducing two metric tensors corresponding to two interacting gravitational fields. These gravitational fields interact to form a coupled system consisting of two different gravitational wave modes: one corresponding to a massless graviton and the other to a massive graviton.

While the coupling of the two metrics is mathematically defined, the underlying physical mechanism that would provide an explanation for this coupling remains unclear and is not explicitly physically described.

The intersecting fields model suggests a possible physical mechanism coupling the gravitational fields by considering the dynamics and types of the interacting curvatures: a positive convex curvature asso-

ciated with an expanding field (which may be related to the massless graviton), and a negative concave curvature associated with a contracting field (which may be related to the massive graviton).

The expanding field generates an outward pulling effect with its outer convex side, similar to that caused by a cosmological constant, with long-range influence, while the contracting field produces a localized pushing effect with its inner concave side.

When these two fields vary out of phase — for example, a left field contracting while a right field expands — a central manifold of interaction emerges in the coupled system. In these regions, the left-hand curvature of a right expanding field and the right-hand curvature of a left contracting field become intertwined, forming a shared structure composed of four subfields, each one with double curvature coupled by a singularity point.

Each subfield exhibits double curvature, which can be seen as a single curvature with two different sectors or components: one component corresponding to the curvature of the expanding field and the other to the curvature of the contracting field. The double curvature within these subfields can be either doubly positive, doubly negative, or a combination of half-positive and half-negative curvatures (depending on the phases of variation of the intersecting fields), coupled or united at a singularity point where the intersecting gravitational fields meet.

A bigravity theory modeled in this way would potentially provide a description of the singularity points inside black holes as abrupt changes in curvature generated by the coupling of the two types of interacting curvatures. However, the current mathematical framework of bigravity theory does not associate the interacting fields with positive or negative curvatures that expand or contract. It does not predict a manifold of subfields shared by the coupled system, and it does not propose that curvatures are coupled through a singularity point. Additionally, bigravity theory does not offer a framework for understanding quantum gravitational effects or interactions at the atomic or subatomic scale.

4 Singularities in the Atomic Realm and Bimetric Approaches

Singularities are known to arise at the atomic level within the context of the three fundamental interactions: electromagnetic, strong, and weak. Specifically, in the electromagnetic (EM) field, singularities occur at the 'charge point,' where the field becomes infinite. These infinities are managed through renormalization in Quantum Electrodynamics (QED), which regularizes the divergent quantities but does not fully clarify their physical origin. Similar singularities also emerge in the mathematical formulations of the strong and weak interactions and are handled by renormalization within Quantum Chromodynamics (QCD) and the Electroweak theory, respectively. The Intersecting Fields Model predicts and reinterprets such singularities across all four interactions as abrupt changes in curvature formed by the coupling of two interacting gravitational fields, creating a shared nucleus of subfields. These subfields are characterized by double curvatures with sudden changes in sign or direction, paralleling the curvature singularities the model predicts for black holes. This reinterpretation suggests a deeper structural origin of singularities, offering a unified framework to understand their behavior across different interactions.

5 Supersymmetric Dual Atomic Nucleus

The intersecting fields model is proposed as a deterministic, non-probabilistic "bigravitational" atom whose nucleus is formed by the coupled interaction of two gravitational fields. It suggests that the inward-pushing force from the negative curvature (of a contracting field) and the outward-pulling force from the positive curvature (of an expanding field) interact to form different subfield-particles: a doubly compressed subfield-particle for the strong interaction, a doubly decompressed subfield-particle for the weak interaction, and a half-compressed, half-decompressed subfield-particle for the electromag-

netic interaction.

Figure 2: *Bigravitational antisymmetric system: nuclear fermionic particles*

The subfields will act as fermionic or bosonic particles, being topologically transformed into each other through time without the need of additional superpartners in the following way:

With opposite phases, the upper vertical subfield will move right or left toward the side of the host field that contracts. Moving leftwards, that subfield will act as an electron. The pushing force generated by the outer positive side of its left curvature when moving left is interpreted as an electric charge. On the right side of the system, that vertical subfield will exist as a virtual particle; that is, it will not currently exist but will later appear as a positron subfield mov-

ing rightwards when the left field expands and the right contracts.

The pendular displacements of this subfield allow us to describe it as a Majorana antiparticle, a particle that is its own antiparticle at different times.

The inner curvature of this vertical subfield is formed by two negative curvatures united by a cusp point; it also can be considered as a single negative curvature that abruptly changes direction at its central singularity point.

Simplifying its curvature in a 2D model, we can say that acting as a positron, when the right field expands and the left one expands, the subfield's right side curvature is formed by the negative curvature inside the right-handed half part of the left expanding field, and the subfield's left curvature is formed by the negative side of the curvature inside the left half part of the right contracting field.

At that same stage, when the right field contracts and the left one expands, the right transverse subfield receives a double pushing force that contracts it: one caused by the positive outer side of the right-handed half part of the left expanding field, and another caused by the inner negative curvature of the left half part of the right contracting field. At that moment, the left transverse subfield does not exhibit symmetry because it will be experiencing a double decompression: Its upper positive curvature will move rightwards because it is formed by the outer side of the half part of the right contracting field; and its bottom negative curvature will also move right because it is formed by the negative side of the right half part of the left expansive field.

The subfield that contracts increases its inner kinetic orbital energy and its mass density, creating a stronger bond that unites the system. The subfield that expands decreases its inner kinetic energy and its mass density, representing a weaker bond in the interactions that allow the nucleus and the whole system to remain united.

When the left field contracts and the right one expands, the left transverse subfield will contract, reaching mirror symmetry with the previous stage of the right transverse contracting subfield, which now will be expanding.

The left expanding transverse subfield at moment 1

will be the mirror antiparticle of the right expanding transverse subfield at moment 2; and the left contracting transverse subfield at moment 2 will be the antiparticle of the right contracting subfield at moment 1. These would be Dirac antiparticles.

Figure 3: *Bigravitational Symmetric system: nuclear bosonic particles.*

These topological transformations represent an oscillatory flux of transfer density and energy between the left and right sides of the system.

In this antisymmetric system, the singularity point will move left or right of the center of the system, toward the side of the fields that contract.

In the context of this dual atomic model, the right contracting transverse subfield is predicted to be a contracting proton that decays into a neutrino when

expanding; the right expanding transverse subfield is proposed to be an antineutrino that becomes an antiproton when contracting. Neutrons are characterized in this model as the neutral stage where the negative and positive sides of the system annihilate their charges because the vertical subfields pass through the vertical axis that determines the center of the system, and the transverse subfields exhibit the same shape and density during the short moment when the left and right fields have the same curvature while contracting and expanding (or expanding and contracting).

Antisymmetry is introduced in the system because of a delay in the phase of one of the intersecting fields. This implies the necessity of an additional time dimension represented by a coordinate that moves—in a type of Wick rotation—from the imaginary coordinate Y to a purely imaginary coordinate represented by a diagonal axis.

As the vertical subfield cannot simultaneously be at the left and right sides, and the transverse subfields cannot be simultaneously expanding or simultaneously contracting, they can be considered governed by an exclusion principle. Considering Pauli's principle in the context of mirror symmetry or antisymmetric field-particles, we could state that the four subfields in this antisymmetric system would be fermions.

When the phases of the intersecting fields synchronize, the upper central subfield will move upwards while contracting, receiving a double inward force caused by the negative side of the left half part of the right field's curvature, and by the negative side of the right half part of the left field's curvature. The singularity point will move upwards through the central Y axis. The double force of compression would cause an upward pushing force that can be interpreted as Hawking radiation in the context of cosmological black holes, a pulsation that emits a photon in an atomic realm.

When a moment later both intersecting fields expand, the vertical subfield will expand moving downwards, losing its inner density and slowing its inner kinetic orbital energy. This decay that occurs in the concave side of the system does not imply a loss of information because an equivalent inverted force will

emerge at the convex side of the system, where an inverted cone of light with a double positive curvature connected by the singularity point receives the compression caused by the positive side of the right half part of the left expanding field, and by the positive side of the left half part of the right expanding field. This inverted pulsation would cause an antiphoton. Photon and antiphoton would follow the Exclusion principle.

Figure 4: *Singularities in the symmetric system when both intersecting fields expand.*

However, in the symmetric system, the transverse subfields have chiral symmetry; they simultaneously contract or expand, being interchangeable under rotation. As the left and right transverse subfields simultaneously contract or simultaneously expand, their states of being contracting or expanding would not be ruled by the Pauli Exclusion Principle, being characterized as bosons.

Individually considered, each intersecting field has a smooth curvature with no singularity; if they were separately considered black holes, they would fit with Kerr's statements about the non-mandatory existence of singularities in black holes.

However, considered as a system, it can be said that although singularity points exist inside the "trapped" transverse subfields and in the vertical subfields, a singularity point does exist on the outer side of the black hole systems, below Penrose's event horizon, representing a counterexample to Penrose's censorship conjecture.

The inner singularity of the subfield placed at the convex side of the system will be seen naked by an ob-

server at a distance looking at the convex side of the black hole system. Its inner kinetic energy and material density will be considered dark by an observer placed in the concave side of the system.

Initially, it can be thought that the dynamics of the system can be described by two separate functions: a complex differential function that describes the evolution of the symmetric system, and a complex conjugate differential function which describes the evolution of the antisymmetric system. Even if they synchronize and desynchronize periodically, those smooth and continuous transformations would respond to the traditional continuity of classical wave mechanics. Then, where does the quantum behaviour originate from?

By representing the pushing forces caused by the inner or outer curvatures of the expanding or contracting fields with eigenvectors of value 1 or -1, and representing those eigenvectors as the elements of a set of 2x2 complex rotational matrices, the evolution of the vectors indicates an interpolation between the symmetric complex and the antisymmetric complex conjugate moments of a rotational system:

Figure 5: *Rotational system: eigenvectors evolution interpolates the symmetric and the antisymmetric systems.*

A first symmetric stage where both intersecting fields contract. A second antisymmetric stage where the right field contracts and the left expands. A third symmetric stage where both intersecting fields expand. A fourth antisymmetric stage where the left intersecting field contracts and the right expands. The nuclear transformations in curvature through these stages imply a total of $4 \times 4 = 16$ singularities, which relates this composite model with a Kummer-type surface and thus with algebraic geometry.

Along with the abrupt changes in the smoothness of the curvature of the nuclear subfields, the discontinuity derived from that unexpected interpolation

may be interpreted as a quantum jump in the continuous development of a classical wave function.

6 Discussion and Outlook: Innovations and Open Possibilities

While the intersecting fields model presented in this paper lacks a rigorous algebraic formalism, a mathematical background has been added to the model in a previous paper Bueno [2023a] and Bueno [2023b], characterizing in a conceptual way the curvature singularities with Gorenstein theory, offering insights into the mass gap problem and reflection positivity. It also describing the interpolation between the symmetric and antisymmetric transformations of the nuclear subfields as Hodge cycles related to Tomita-Takesaki theory.

The model offers a comprehensive and integrative framework that draws connections between previously separate theories across both cosmology and quantum physics, aiming to provide a coherent set of conceptual tools and predictions that may inspire further research and the development of a more formal mathematical structure.

The model's innovative contributions and open possibilities include:

- **A Unified Geometric Framework for General Relativity and Quantum Mechanics:** The model proposes a unified geometric framework that aims to bridge general relativity and quantum mechanics. By conceptualizing a deterministic atomic structure, it unifies all known fundamental interactions, aligning with the work of t'Hooft. This framework provides a comprehensive, non-probabilistic perspective on the atomic structure, offering an integrated view of gravitational, electromagnetic, strong, and weak forces within a singular topological model.
- **Counterexample to the Cosmic Censorship Conjecture:** The framework suggests a possible counterexample to Penrose's Cosmic

Censorship Conjecture by proposing the existence of naked singularities visible from certain perspectives. Moreover, it posits that these singularities are linked to regions of space that appear "dark" to some observers, potentially offering connections to the phenomena of dark matter and dark energy. The model also predicts upward and downward, or leftward and rightward, displacements in the singularity point with respect to the center of the system.

- **Singularities in Subatomic Particles:** Extending the concept of singularities to the quantum realm, the model hypothesizes the existence of curvature singularities within subatomic particles. This perspective aims to provide a unified topological description of spacetime across both cosmological and quantum scales.
- **A Physical Mechanism for Bigravity Theories:** By proposing an interaction mechanism for two metric tensors—each representing distinct gravitational curvatures—the model provides a conceptual foundation for bigravity theories. It extends these concepts to the atomic scale, thereby offering a non-standard "quantum bigravity" model that integrates massive and massless gravitons through intersecting gravitational field singularities.
- **Proton Decay Mechanism via Model Dynamics:** The dynamics of the model provide a mechanism for proton decay, suggesting that interactions between symmetric and antisymmetric curvatures facilitate this process. The decay is conceived through topological changes in the field structure, offering a new perspective on how proton instability can arise from underlying gravitational interactions.
- **Periodic Transfer of Density and Energy Between Symmetric and Antisymmetric Sides:** The model proposes periodic transfers of density and energy between the symmetric and antisymmetric sides of the system. These transfers, while preserving the total Hamiltonian, offer a way to integrate concepts from "hand-shaking" theories, where events and interactions

are mediated through time-symmetric processes. This periodic exchange provides a novel way to describe the balance of forces and conservation laws within the system.

- **Topological Nature of Singularities and Curvature Discontinuities:** The model reinterprets singularities in black holes and subatomic particles as topological features characterized by abrupt curvature discontinuities, unlike the gradual spacetime curvatures predicted by General Relativity.
- **Singularities in the Atomic Realm and Bimetric Connections:** The model identifies singularities at the atomic level as abrupt changes in curvature formed by the coupling of two interacting fields, similar to the model's prediction for black holes. Singularities at the atomic scale have been managed by renormalization in QED, which regularizes infinities but does not fully resolve the underlying nature of these singularities. The presence of double curvatures and singularities in the nuclear subfields proposed by the model offers a novel perspective, suggesting that a framework involving a dual system of two coupled fields may be necessary to fully understand these singularities.
- **Renormalization of Singularities in the Atomic Realm and Connections to Bimetric Theory:** At the atomic level, singularities manifest as infinities in the mathematical formulations of all three fundamental interactions: the electromagnetic, strong, and weak forces. These infinities have been regularized through renormalization in Quantum Electrodynamics (QED), Quantum Chromodynamics (QCD), and the Electroweak theory. However, while renormalization handles these infinities mathematically, the physical meaning behind their emergence remains unexplained. The intersecting fields model proposes a novel perspective, suggesting that these singularities represent abrupt changes in curvature formed by the coupling of two interacting fields, much like the model's predictions for black hole singularities. This leads to

the idea that a framework involving a dual system of coupled fields may be necessary to fully understand the nature of these singularities.

- **Bigravitational Higgs-like Mechanism:** The model proposes a mechanism similar to the Higgs mechanism, where mass generation arises from the dynamics of bi-gravitational fields. Rather than relying on the traditional scalar Higgs field, the model utilizes longitudinal wave mechanics, suggesting that periodic variations in the curvature of intersecting bi-gravitational fields produce "pushing" and "pulling" forces that give rise to the masses of particles. This gravitational reinterpretation provides an alternative perspective on the origin of mass and energy, offering a bigravitational framework that parallels the role of the Higgs mechanism in the Standard Model.
- **Connection to Quantum Chromodynamics (QCD):** The model connects to QCD by representing the pushing and pulling forces within the system as vectors in a vector space. These vectors, interpreted as quarks, offer a novel geometric perspective on the color force and the strong interaction, framing quarks as fundamental carriers of force within the model's topological structure.
- **Duality in Field Dynamics and Holographic Interpretation:** The intersecting gravitational fields produce vertical and transverse subfields, resembling mirrored regions connected by cusp singularities. This structure suggests a possible holographic nature to the system, where the dynamics of the entire space may be encoded within lower-dimensional manifolds, akin to ideas in the holographic principle.
- **Geometric Interpretation of Charge and Force through Curvature:** The model provides a deterministic interpretation of charge and force as outcomes of the curvature in gravitational fields. Specifically, electric charge is viewed as a "pushing" force resulting from the curvature of expanding or contracting fields offering a unified geometric approach that links gravity with electromagnetic interactions.
- **Supersymmetry without Superpartners:** The model introduces a novel perspective on supersymmetry, conceptualizing it as a topological transformation within a rotational dual intersecting fields system. Unlike conventional supersymmetric theories that rely on additional superpartners, this framework describes how subfields transform between fermions and bosons, achieving supersymmetry through topological oscillations influenced by the system's rotational dynamics.
- **Integration of Calabi-Yau Structures and Conifold Singularities:** The model establishes a connection between the transverse subfields of the dual gravitational system and Calabi-Yau structures, such as elliptic fibrations and conifold singularities encountered in string theory. Notably, the framework retains the complex extra-dimensional structure inherent to these topological features, without reducing or compactifying the spatial dimensions.
- **Dynamic Phase Synchronization and Asymmetry in Gravitational Interactions:** By accounting for phase differences between intersecting gravitational fields, the model provides a mechanism for dynamic symmetry-breaking and synchronization. The interplay between synchronized and desynchronized phases offers insights into the origin of asymmetry in gravitational systems and its potential cosmological implications.
- **Additional Time Dimension and Phase Differences:** A purely imaginary additional time dimension is introduced to account for phase differences within the gravitational system. This dimension enables a description of antisymmetry in the phases of nuclear antisymmetric subfields or between the symmetric subfields and intersecting fields.

- **Insights into the Mass Gap, Reflection Positivity, and Hodge Cycles:** By employing Gorenstein theory to characterize curvature singularities, the model offers potential explanations for the mass gap problem and reflection positivity. Additionally, it suggests interpolations between the smooth continuous transformations of symmetric and antisymmetric moments within the system, resulting in unexpected discontinuities in complex or conjugate wave functions. These interpolations and related transformations are interpreted as Hodge cycles, which manifest in the periodic transformations of a Kummer-type surface, thereby providing a connection to complex geometry and algebraic structures.
- **Quantum Jumps as Curvature Discontinuities:** The model interprets quantum jumps as discontinuities in curvature interpolation between symmetric and antisymmetric states. This provides a topological framework for quantum transitions, suggesting that what appear as probabilistic quantum events may be understood as deterministic transformations in the curvature of intersecting gravitational fields.
- **Visual Representation of Atomic Structure and Abstract Algebraic Concepts:** The model provides a visual and geometric framework for understanding the structure and evolution of the atomic nucleus, curvature singularities, and highly abstract algebraic concepts such as Gorenstein liaison and Hodge cycles. By interpreting these mathematical structures through the lens of curvature and topological dynamics, the model bridges the gap between algebraic abstraction and geometric intuition, offering an accessible and intuitive perspective on complex structures in both geometry and physics.

Keywords: black holes, singularities, Cosmic Censorship Conjecture, intersecting gravitational fields, bi-gravity, bi metric tensors, dual gravitational fields, information paradox, mirror symmetry, strong and

weak interactions, electromagnetic interactions, supersymmetry, naked singularities, quantum field theory, General relativity, quantum gravity, Gorenstein liaison, Hodge cycles, Kummer surfaces, T-duality, reflection positivity, SYZ conjecture, mass gap problem, equivalence principle.

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Appendix: Reinterpreting Gravity and Acceleration: A Single-Field Approach Without Curvature Singularities

This appendix outlines an alternative interpretation of gravity, weight, gravitational acceleration, and the Einstein's equivalence principle, which considers gravity and acceleration as equivalent sides of the same phenomenon. This perspective focuses on the dynamic role of gravitational fields as longitudinal waves and the distinctions between different masses involved in gravitational interactions.

It considers a single gravitational field with smooth curvature, distinct from the main model's framework of two coupled fields sharing a manifold where singularities in curvature are predicted and described. This single-field approach provides a reinterpretation of gravitational acceleration without invoking curvature singularities within the field, aligning with the equivalence principle by describing how acceleration is perceived in varying frames of reference.

1. Distinction Between Different Types of Masses in Gravitational Systems

To understand the dynamics of gravity and its effects, we must differentiate between three main types of masses:

Mass of the Gravitational Source: This refers to the mass of the object (such as a planet or star) that creates the gravitational field and curvature in space-time. This field behaves as a longitudinal wave that expands and contracts. The gravitational source and its associated curved field move through space, often orbiting around another object, such as a star or galaxy.

Mass of Surface Objects: These are masses located on the surface of the gravitational source. They experience weight as a function of their density when pushed by the planetary mass, which is in motion through space. Importantly, surface objects do not directly interact with the gravitational field in the way orbital objects do because they are not in orbit

within the curved field; rather, their experience of "weight" is due to the pressure from the motion of the planetary mass.

Mass of Orbital Objects: These are objects that orbit within the gravitational field created by the source mass. Their movement is governed by the kinetic forces of the expanding and contracting gravitational field, which acts as a dynamic wave that interacts with these objects.

This distinction is essential to understanding how gravitational interactions differ based on whether an object is on the surface of a source mass or orbiting within its gravitational field.

2. Orbital Motion and Dynamic Gravitational Fields

In conventional terms, objects in orbit are seen as being in "free fall" within the curved space-time created by the source mass. However, in this alternative model, the gravitational field itself is a dynamic longitudinal wave, acting as a shock wave on the source mass, expanding and contracting as the source mass moves through space.

Orbital objects are influenced by the kinetic forces generated by the longitudinal wave of the gravitational field when contracting or expanding. Their motion is not simply a passive path through static curvature but is actively shaped by the changes in the field as it contracts or expands.

The orbital object's mass and density play a role in how it resists the kinetic effects of the field. The orbital motions are not considered inertial but dynamic, receiving a pushing force that accelerates them when the field contracts or slows down when the field expands. The only inertial motion would exist during intervals of no variation in the field (a non-time interval, as time in this model is defined as the measure of the variation in space itself), occurring once the curved field reaches its highest rate of expansion or contraction and then begins a new contraction or expansion.

3. Weight of Surface Objects and Gravitational Acceleration

For surface objects, their "weight" is traditionally interpreted in Newtonian terms as the force of gravitational attraction. However, this model proposes that the weight experienced by these objects arises from the push of the planetary mass as it moves through space. The mass of the planet exerts a force on surface objects, and their weight depends on their density and the pressure experienced due to the planet's motion.

When a surface object is elevated and "falls" back to the planet, the acceleration of the fall is the same for all surface objects, regardless of their density. This is because the acceleration depends on the movement of the planet through space towards the objects it encounters, not on the properties of the falling objects. It is the planet that moves towards the objects, which are not actually "falling."

The planet's acceleration is influenced by its interaction with its related longitudinal wave, which pushes against the planet's density, acting as a shock wave and creating varying degrees of curvature amplitude.

The gravitational acceleration of "falling objects" is not a direct consequence of the gravitational curvature; rather, it is related to how the curvature is formed by the planet's density interacting with a pushing field that moves the planet through space. When the planet experiences greater resistance to this pushing field, a higher curvature is produced, resulting in a stronger pushing force and an increase in the planet's velocity toward the falling objects. This curvature can be thought of as protecting the falling objects from being directly influenced by the pushing field that drives the planet's movement toward them.

Thus, the gravitational acceleration experienced by surface objects is directly tied to the planet's own movement and how its mass interacts with the dynamic longitudinal wave of its gravitational field. This acceleration is uniform for any object that "falls" onto the planet's surface, regardless of the object's density.

4. The Curvature of Space-Time.

Instead of treating the curvature of space-time as a static property intrinsic to mass, this model proposes that curvature arises mechanically and dynamically from the interaction between the source mass's density and a pushing field. This curvature is created when the field is resisted by the mass. The resulting gravitational curvature behaves like a pushing longitudinal wave, reflecting how the mass accelerates or decelerates through space.

A higher resistance due to greater density implies greater thermodynamic friction, which gradually alters the mass distribution, reducing its density and thereby relaxing the curvature amplitude. As friction decreases, the mass distribution compacts again, increasing resistance and curvature amplitude, leading to periodic contractions and expansions.

The gravitational effects felt by both surface and orbital objects are thus a result of different aspects of the dynamic wave-like behavior of the gravitational field and the movement of the source mass through space.

5. Differences from Newtonian Gravity and General Relativity

In Newtonian gravity, gravitational acceleration is explained as a force of attraction between two masses. The force depends on the product of their masses and the inverse square of the distance between them. This alternative model does not rely on a direct "attraction" between masses. Instead, gravitational acceleration is seen as a consequence of the planet's movement through space and its interaction with a longitudinal wave that influences the uniformity of the acceleration felt by any surface object, independent of its own mass.

In GR, gravity is not a force but a manifestation of the curvature of space-time caused by mass and energy. Objects follow geodesics in this curved space-time, and what we perceive as "falling" or "orbiting" is the natural path within that curvature. It provides mathematical equations to describe how mass and energy curve space-time, but it does not give a mechanical explanation for how this curvature arises or how

the experience of weight is generated in this context. In contrast, this model provides a wave-mechanical explanation by suggesting that gravitational acceleration of falling objects is not directly caused by the curvature of the gravitational field but by the displacement of the planet towards the separated objects. The field curvature is an indication of the force of pressure that is moving the planet through space and toward the objects it meets in that travel, as well as the planetary velocity. This resistance generates the dynamic wave interactions that affect the gravitational acceleration or deceleration of orbiting objects and their orbital paths.

6. Influence of Rotating Reference Frames on Perceived Acceleration

In this model, the path of a falling object is fundamentally a straight line through space. However, when observed from the surface of a rotating planet, the object's trajectory appears curved. This curvature is not due to the object interacting with the gravitational field's curvature in space-time but rather due to the planet's rotation.

When an object falls vertically, it follows a straight path relative to the surrounding space. However, the rotation of the planet underneath creates the perception of a curved trajectory because the observer's frame of reference is constantly changing. This is similar to how the path of a cannonball appears to curve when fired on a rotating Earth: the actual path is straight, but the rotating surface makes it appear otherwise.

Additionally, the distance covered by a falling object can be seen as a diagonal when measured from the starting to ending points of the fall. Since the planet rotates during the fall, the diagonal path is measured in a reference frame that changes over time. This change introduces a perceived stretching or contraction in the distance and time of the fall, which might be mistakenly interpreted as a "gravitational acceleration."

An analogy can be made to the diagonal of a square. If the diagonal is measured using the frame of reference of the square's sides, it introduces a slight distortion due to the angle and rotation, causing a

perceived difference in length and time. In a similar way, the falling object's straight-line path becomes "dilated" or "contracted" when viewed from the planet's rotating frame of reference.

Therefore, the perception of the object's acceleration or deceleration is partly due to this rotational effect and the relative change in the observer's frame, not solely from gravitational attraction. The object's true path through space remains straight, but the planet's movement and rotation cause a relative curvature and apparent acceleration when measured from the rotating surface.

7. Influence of Atmospheric Pressure on Perceived Acceleration

In addition to the effects of rotation, the weight of the atmosphere sitting on the planetary surface significantly influences the observed acceleration of a falling object. As an object descends, it encounters progressively denser atmospheric layers, similar to how a diver experiences higher pressure as they go deeper underwater.

This gradient of air pressure exerts an increasing "attractive pulling" force on the falling object, enhancing its acceleration as it approaches the surface. The denser air closer to sea level applies more pressure to the object, which contributes to its observed increase in velocity.

However, it is important to note that this effect depends on the density and shape of the falling object. In a real atmosphere, objects with different densities or aerodynamic profiles will fall at different rates due to varying air resistance. This diverges from the idealized case of uniform acceleration observed in vacuum conditions, where objects fall at the same rate regardless of their mass or density. Hence, experiments demonstrating uniform fall velocities are typically performed in conditions of emptiness (vacuum), where atmospheric effects are absent.

Therefore, the acceleration of a falling object is affected both by the planet's rotation and by the increasing atmospheric pressure. These factors, along with the object's own properties, influence the perceived trajectory and speed of the fall.

8. Acceleration in Vacuum and Referential Metrics: A Bi-gravity Analogy

In a vacuum, this model interprets the acceleration of falling objects not as a force of attraction but as a consequence of the interplay between two reference metrics: the rotated coordinate system of the planet and the unrotated coordinate system of the object's straight-line path.

The rotated metric, linked to the planet's frame of reference, introduces perceived dilation or contraction in space and time. This occurs as the object's trajectory is measured relative to the curved path of the rotating surface. It is analogous to measuring the diagonal of a square based on its sides, which distorts the spatial-temporal perception and leads to apparent acceleration without invoking traditional gravitational attraction. Since velocity is a function of distance and time, the perceived stretching or compression of distances in this metric causes changes in the time needed to traverse them, resulting in a perceived acceleration (if the distance appears shorter) or deceleration (if the distance appears longer).

If an observer, without recognizing the difference between the rotated and unrotated reference frames, measures a diagonal path as if it were a vertical straight-line descent, this would introduce an artificial shortening of the perceived distance. This shortening would then be misinterpreted as an increase in speed, as the object would seem to traverse the "shorter" distance more quickly.

Conversely, if the actual straight-line path is longer than perceived (due to the misalignment of the frames), the speed would appear artificially decreased, as the object would seem to take more time to cover what is thought to be a longer path.

In reality, the object is moving through a straight-line path displaced rightwards or leftwards in the unrotated reference frame, and the perceived change in velocity is thus an artifact of the rotated frame's misrepresentation of the real path.

The unrotated metric represents the object's true straight-line path through space. The perceived acceleration is thus a result of the discrepancy between these metrics, where the rotation of the planet distorts measurements of distance and time.

This duality between rotated and unrotated metrics resembles bimetric theories, which describe spacetime through two interacting metrics. As discussed in the context of the intersecting fields topology, bimetric theories involve two coupled gravitational fields, each with its own metric, interpreted in the intersecting fields model as abrupt changes in direction.

In the single-field scenario, relating the rotated and unrotated metrics may produce singularities as infinitesimal quantities in the distorted distance, introducing irrational measures similar to the diagonal of a square relative to its sides. These types of singularities, however, do not occur in the gravitational curvature.

Moreover, this dual perspective resonates with the conceptual framework of General Relativity (GR), as both theories consider the influence of different frames of reference on the perception of motion. However, this model diverges by offering a more 'pure' relativistic view of gravitational acceleration. The key difference lies in the interpretation of acceleration:

- In GR, acceleration is a physical effect caused by the curvature of space-time. Moving inertially through a statically curved space, objects follow geodesics, which are locally straight paths within this curved space-time. This curvature, dictated by Einstein's field equations, causes the physical acceleration of a falling object. From an external perspective, these geodesics appear curved, a feature distinct from the physical curvature of the planet's surface.
- In contrast, this model proposes that acceleration in a vacuum is not caused by gravitational force in the traditional sense but by the relation between the rotated frame of the planet and the unrotated straight-line path of the falling object. The perceived acceleration stems from the distortion of the object's spatial-temporal path when observed from the rotating frame of reference, leading to perceived changes in distance and velocity.

In this model, the curvature relevant to perceived

acceleration pertains to the rotating curved planet, not to space-time itself.

While relativity addresses how observers perceive space, time, and motion differently, GR models gravity through a static curvature of space-time with geodesics defining the trajectories of objects. However, it does not fully explore how the dynamic relationship between the rotating planetary frame and the unrotated frame of a falling object might affect the perception of acceleration.

Incorporating a dynamic wave-mechanical interpretation of gravitational fields, rather than a static space-time curvature, would result in significant theoretical differences.

Reinterpreting acceleration as an effect of differing reference frames aligns more closely with a relativistic wave-mechanics perspective, where gravitational fields are dynamic and oscillatory. This interpretation reframes acceleration not as a force derived from space-time curvature but as a consequence of relative motion between the planet's rotating reference frame and the object's straight-line path.

Such a relativistic interpretation of gravitational acceleration, emphasizing differing reference frames and perceived motion, could provide a novel perspective on the accelerating expansion and potential contraction of the universe.